

IPBES BBA Chapter 5 – Literature reviews for Chapter 5 / IPBES business and biodiversity assessment

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Project Leader

Tuan Nguyen (tuan.nguyen@uhasselt.be)

Researchers

Amrei von Hase (ahase@wcs.org)

Laura Sonter (laura.sonter@thebiodiversityconsultancy.com)

Felicia Lasmana (felicia.lasmana@gmail.com)

Hishmi Husain (hishmi.husain@tatasteel.com)

Jacquette Adam (jacquette@exigent.co.za)

Marie-Helene Enrici (marie-helene.enrici@solvay.com)

Natalia Lutti Hummel Wicher (natalialuttihummel@gmail.com)

Pippa Howard (Pippa.Howard@naturemetrics.co.uk)

Steven Dickinson (Steven.dickinson@totalenergies.com)

Thao Fabregas (fabregas.thao@gmail.com)

Divya Narain (divya.narain@smithschool.ox.ac.uk)

Data Curators

Alina Vera Paz (tsu.bizbiodiversity@gmail.com)

Olena Tarasova-Krasiieva (olena.tarasova-krasiieva@unep-wcmc.org)

Rainer Krug (rainer.krug@senckenberg.de)

Aidin Niamir (aidin.niamir@senckenberg.de)

Description

This report describes the process of literature collection and review in Chapter 5 of the IPBES business and biodiversity assessment. Two separate teams conducted the literature search to identify, characterize, and assess different frameworks, initiatives, viewpoints, and conceptualizations of businesses and financial institutions' roles and responsibilities, motivations, challenges, barriers, and opportunities to action, and options for actions to contribute to global biodiversity objectives and transformative change (Groups A, B). The approach to the literature search includes three steps. First, a set of key literature is identified using expert knowledge. Then, a snowball search is conducted based on the identified literature to supplement the body of literature. The snowball search results in a limited number of selected scientific and grey literature, which is partly due to the rapidly evolving nature of the topic. As a result, a final step involves supplementing the scientific and grey literature identified by the experts. The final literature identified is pooled together, reviewed, and used throughout the Chapter where relevant. The final step of the literature search ran until July 2024.

Besides scientific literature, grey literature is an important aspect of Chapter 5. The diverse background of Chapter 5 experts allowed compiling a wide source of grey literature, covering different business-related aspects, such as sector, geographical location, business size, and the perspectives of different stakeholder groups (e.g., Indigenous Peoples and local communities reports, policy documents, practitioner guidance, etc.). Chapter experts also consulted researchers working on the topic for literature suggestions, searched the websites of various organizations working on the topic regularly, and followed new publication alerts and their reference lists.

Experts also supplemented the literature collection with documents specifically requested by the external reviewers.

Process overview

Protocol

1. Literature Search

- **Type of analysis/search/review:** Literature search
- **Key paper selection:** experts' selection
- **Searched period:** September 2023 to January 2024

An initial set of 18 key papers was identified through expert knowledge by two groups of experts in support of different sections of the Chapter during the First Author Meeting. Group A consists of 3 experts, looking at the literature on the roles and responsibilities of business in contributing to transformative change and sustainable development to achieve the 2050 Vision for Biodiversity. Group B consists of 4 experts, looking at the literature on the motivations, challenges, barriers, and opportunities of businesses in taking action. Group A identified 6 key papers, and Group B identified 12 key papers. These key papers set the basis for the snowball search method in the next step.

2. Snowball search for Group A and B

Type of analysis/search/review: Snowball search for articles indexed in OpenAlex

- **Search language(s):** English
- **Search engine:** OpenAlex
- **Search dates:** 28 January 2024, 30 January 2024
- **Location of data:** IPBES_BBA_5.1_07-2024_(A), IPBES_BBA_5.1_07-2024_(B)

The second step, employing the snowball search method, was conducted separately by Group A and Group B. In each group, experts collected the DOI links from the key articles identified from the first step and ran a snowball search on the DOI links using the openalexR package in R software. This package allows for connecting and retrieving bibliographic information from OpenAlex, including the title and abstract of the articles. The experts screened the resulting literature, containing 281 records for Group A and 740 records for Group B, and selected 23 and 81 relevant records in each Group for in-depth review, respectively. This step only allows additional literature with a DOI link (often scientific literature) to be selected. In total, 104 additional records were selected for in-depth review in this step.

3. Scientific and grey literature search supplemented by experts

Type of analysis/search/review: Grey literature
Search language(s): English
Key paper selection: experts' selection
Searched period: September 2023 to July 2024

Chapter 5's literature is further supplemented with scientific and grey literature via an extended period of literature collection between June 2023 and July 2024, using expert knowledge. Since the topic in review is rapidly evolving and new evidence continuously emerges, this approach allows the Chapter experts to identify and review the most up-to-date developments in the topic.

Experts use their diverse networks to remain updated on new literature or reports relevant to the topics of the Chapter, including approaches such as following the LinkedIn profiles of organizations and researchers whose work is relevant to the topic of business and biodiversity, requesting literature suggestions from researchers working on the topic, visiting organizations and initiatives' publications and resources websites, and subscribing to new publication alerts from these websites.

Several organizations and initiatives are working (or have worked) on the topic of business and biodiversity. The Chapters experts conducted a one-time screening of the websites of these organizations and initiatives, and followed their networks using the approaches mentioned above for new publication alerts. These organizations and initiatives include, but are not limited to:

- Align Project
- Boston Consulting Group
- Business for Nature
- Business and Biodiversity Offsets Programme
- Cambridge Conservation Initiative
- Capital Coalition
- CDC Biodiversité
- CDP
- Conservation International
- Council for Sustainable Development
- European Business & Biodiversity Platform
- Fauna & Flora (formerly Fauna & Flora International)
- Finance for Biodiversity
- It's Now for Nature campaign
- Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services
- International Union for Conservation of Nature
- Nature Positive Alliance
- Oxford Nature Positive Hub
- Principles for Responsible Investment
- Science Based Targets Network
- Taskforce on Nature-related Financial Disclosures
- UN Environment Programme World Conservation Monitoring Centre
- UN Environment Programme Finance Initiative
- We Mean Business Coalition
- Wildlife Conservation Society
- World Benchmarking Alliance
- World Business Council for Sustainable Development
- World Economic Forum
- World Wide Fund for Nature

4. Scientific and grey literature search supplemented by external reviewers

Finally, the additional body of literature suggested by external reviewers is reviewed, and selected works are incorporated into the relevant sections of Chapter 5. Works selected by the expert group to include in the Chapter support a balance representation of current and emerging concepts, viewpoints, and examples in the topic, with a particular focus on addressing the gaps identified by the external reviewers.